

EDTA and CN^- interfere. Even trace amount of Au^{3+} interferes with Pd^{2+} estimation.

Results and Discussion

The precipitations of Ni^{2+} and Pd^{2+} complexes commence at pH 5.0 and 1.0 and are quantitative within the pH ranges 6-10 and 1.5-10, respectively. At least 1.5 times the theoretical amounts of the reagent are needed for complete precipitation of metal ions. Ethanolic solution of the reagent was found stable for several weeks. The complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents. Nickel and palladium complexes melt with decomposition at 253 and 285°, respectively. Analytical results indicate molecular formula, $\text{M}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$.

Infrared spectral bands of the reagent at 1 670, 3 205 and 1 290 cm^{-1} are due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{N}-\text{H}$ and $\text{N}-\text{O}$ stretching vibrations, respectively. In the spectrum of Ni^{2+} or Pd^{2+} complexes, the position of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ band remains unchanged while $\text{N}-\text{H}$ band disappears and a lowering in frequency of $\text{N}-\text{O}$ band is observed, suggesting the bonding through N of $\text{N}-\text{H}$ group after displacement of proton and through O of $\text{N}-\text{O}$ group.

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Use of some Visual Indicators for Direct Titrations with Dibromamine-T

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REDOX titrations in nonaqueous or partially aqueous media are, as a rule, followed potentiometrically. A search through the literature has revealed that the use of visual indicators for titrations in such media is very limited¹⁻⁷. As part of our investigations on novel redox titrants, we explore the possibility of using some visual indica-

tors for direct titrations with dibromamine-T, a typical oxidimetric titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium⁸⁻¹¹.

Experimental

Dibromamine-T (DBT) was prepared⁸ by bromination of chloramine-T (B.D.H.). A decinormal solution ($\sim 0.025 M$) of DBT was prepared by dissolving the dry sample (8.2 g) in anhydrous acetic acid (1 dm^3) and was standardised by the usual iodometric method and stored in an amber-coloured bottle. The six indicator solutions used for the titrations, viz., amaranth, indigo carmine, methyl orange, methyl red, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine and quinoline yellow were prepared by dissolving the dye stuffs in appropriate solvents by standard methods¹². Standard solutions ($\sim 0.1 N$, 500 ml) of potassium antimony tartarate (8.1 g), sodium sulphite (8.2 g), ascorbic acid (4.4 g), hydrazine sulphate (1.6 g), benzhydrazide (2.7 g), isoniazid (1.7 g), phenylhydrazinehydrochloride (1.8 g), semicarbazidehydrochloride (1.4 g), aniline (0.78 g), phenol (0.78 g) and anthranilic acid (1.1 g) were prepared by dissolving the specified amount of these substances in water. As^{3+} solution was prepared by dissolving As_2O_3 (2.5 g) in 1 *N* sodium hydroxide, neutralising it with 1 *N* sulphuric acid and making upto 500 ml with water. Standard solution (500 ml) of Fe^{2+} was prepared by dissolving 19.6 g of ferrous ammonium sulphate (19.6 g) in 2 *N* sulphuric acid and standard solution (500 ml) of 8-hydroxyquinoline (1.8 g) prepared in aqueous acetic acid (50%, v/v). The strengths of these reductant solutions were checked by standard methods^{12,14}.

The metal oxinates of Al^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were prepared by standard methods^{12,13}. To the solutions of the metal salts (2 *M*), an ethanolic solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline (6 *M* for Al^{3+} and 4 *M* for others) was added in small portions with stirring. The precipitated oxinates were filtered, washed with water and dried over P_2O_{10} . Metal anthranilates of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} were prepared by mixing a solution of sodium anthranilate (4 *M*) and the respective metal salts (2 *M*) in neutral or weakly acidic medium. The metal anthranilates were filtered, washed with 0.2% solution of sodium anthranilate and finally with ethanol and dried over P_2O_{10} . Standard solutions of the metal oxinates and anthranilates were prepared by dissolving the required amounts in 500 ml of 2 *N* hydrochloric acid to give approximately 0.1 *N* solutions. The strengths of these solutions were checked by the bromate-bromide method^{12,14}.

The titrations were carried out at room temperature by the following method. To measured aliquots (10-20 ml) of the reductant solution taken in a flask, 2 *N* hydrochloric acid (5 ml) and other reagents such as potassium bromide (0.5 g), sodium acetate (0.5 g), etc., if required, were added. After

diluting the reaction mixture with water to give an overall volume of 100 ml, 2 drops of suitable indicator was added. It was then titrated with standard solution of dibromamine-T to a sharp permanent colour change. A blank titration was done concurrently in each case and no indicator correction was found necessary.

Results and Discussion

The results of the titrations are presented in Table 1. During the redox reaction, DBT is

TABLE 1—DIRECT VISUAL TITRATIONS USING DIBROMAMINE-T (TEN REPLICATES)

Reductant*	Range of concentration studied mmol	Relative mean deviation %	Standard deviation μ mol	Average error %
Arsenic(III)	0.51–0.99	0.23	2.63	0.21
Antimony(III)	0.49–0.99	0.23	2.39	0.22
Iron(II)	0.90–1.90	0.14	1.62	0.14
Sulphite	0.41–0.84	0.14	1.59	0.14
Ascorbic acid	0.48–0.98	0.14	1.75	0.14
Hydrazine	0.31–0.58	0.15	1.77	0.15
Benzhydrazide	0.27–0.54	0.07	0.90	0.07
Isoniazid	0.25–0.52	0.15	1.93	0.15
Phenylhydrazine	0.23–0.46	0.14	1.57	0.14
Semicarbazide	0.24–0.50	0.22	2.21	0.16
Aniline	0.17–0.35	0.12	1.29	0.12
Phenol	0.23–0.43	0.09	1.14	0.09
Oxine	0.22–0.46	0.14	1.19	0.14
Anthranilic acid	0.15–0.31	0.10	1.10	0.10
Al(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₃	0.08–0.16	0.29	1.82	0.15
Mg(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.12–0.26	0.18	1.85	0.18
Mn(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.12–0.26	0.09	1.08	0.09
Co(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.12–0.25	0.15	1.63	0.15
Ni(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.13–0.25	0.14	1.55	0.14
Zn(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.13–0.25	0.14	1.65	0.14
Cd(C ₆ H ₄ ON) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.11–0.24	0.27	2.35	0.19
Mn(C ₇ H ₄ O ₂ N) ₂	0.08–0.17	0.13	1.26	0.11
Co(C ₇ H ₄ O ₂ N) ₂	0.08–0.17	0.14	1.37	0.14
Ni(C ₇ H ₄ O ₂ N) ₂	0.08–0.16	0.14	1.34	0.14
Zn(C ₇ H ₄ O ₂ N) ₂	0.07–0.16	0.14	1.25	0.13
Cd(C ₇ H ₄ O ₂ N) ₂	0.08–0.17	0.13	1.38	0.13

*Quinoline yellow indicator used for all reductants except the metal oxinates, for which methyl red used.

reduced to *p*-toluenesulphonamide as per the half cell reaction,

where, R=CH₃C₆H₄SO₂. The formal potential of the redox couple involved in the oxidant system in glacial acetic acid medium has been reported to be + 1.3 V at 25°, which indicates that DBT is a moderately strong oxidant⁶. From the data presented in Table 1, it is evident that all the 26 reductants can be determined very accurately and precisely by the present direct visual titration method using dibromamine-T as the titrant. Although all the 6 visual indicators are suitable in almost all

the systems studied, quinoline yellow is found to be the best for all but the metal oxinates. In the case of metal oxinates, quinoline yellow does not give sharp end-point due to the colour of the complex in solution. The solutions of all the oxinates in 2 N hydrochloric acid have yellowish green colour, which will mask the colour change from yellow to colourless during the titration using quinoline yellow indicator. Therefore, in this case, methyl red is found to be the most suitable indicator.

Except the systems in which bromination is the actual reaction, all the other systems do not require any addition of bromide. Thus, bromide is to be added for aniline, phenol, oxine, anthranilic acid, and metal oxinates and anthranilates. For all other reductants, there is no need to add bromide, which is a clear advantage of dibromamine-T over other reagents developed earlier. In the case of Fe²⁺, addition of phosphoric acid (5 ml) is essential to remove Fe³⁺ formed *via* complexation and hence, a sharp colour change of the quinoline yellow indicator is possible at the end-point. Moreover, presence of acetate is needed for anthranilic acid and metal anthranilates. In these cases, acetate acts as a catalyst.

All the reductants undergo the usual reactions reported elsewhere. In conformity with the reported reactions, one equivalent of DBT is consumed per mole of Fe²⁺; 2 equiv. for As³⁺, Sb³⁺, sulphite and ascorbic acid; 4 equiv. for hydrazine, benzhydrazide, isoniazid, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide and oxine; 6 equiv. for aniline, phenol and anthranilic acid; 8 equiv. for metal oxinates of Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺; and 12 equiv. for metal oxinate of Al³⁺ and metal anthranilates of Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺.

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Effects of Aquatic Toxic Trace Elements on the Quality of Foodfish

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THE recent discovery of relatively high levels of mercury in fish in North America has focused intense concern on numerous of other potentially toxic elements, such as mercury, copper, zinc, iron, manganese, magnesium, chromium, nickel, calcium, sodium, potassium and others which may be ubiquitous in ecosystems. Trace elements from anthropogenic activities and natural processes enter the marine environment. Such discharges are known to contain organic and inorganic micropollutants including toxic trace elements¹. The fish which live in polluted water may accumulate trace elements, some of which are toxic, from the water *via* their food chains. The fish feeding on small marine organisms, on algae, and on bottom sediments, readily accumulate trace elements, thus endangering human health².

Samples of saltwater fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected. The species composition of the collections generally reflects the

fish populations of the water sampled. Since nutritionally and recreationally fish constitute most important segment of the aquatic ecosystem, toxic elements in fish are obviously of great concern³.

Experimental

Source of materials: Samples of fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected during the summer 1978. The species composition of the collections generally reflects the fish populations of the water sampled. The fish collected were sheepshead (*Diplodus holbrooki*), sea bass (*Monrone saxatilis*), whiting (*Uopycis regius*), grouper (*Garrupa nigriral*), toad fish (*Opsanus tau*), dolphin (*Coryhaena hippurus*), cod (*Gadus morphua*), mullet (*Mugil cephalus*), Red snapper (*Lutianus aya*), silver snapper (*Lutianus grisens*), speckled trout (*Salventinus fontinalis*), and flounder (*Lophopsetta maculata*). The whole fresh fish were placed on ice in an ice-chest and given an identification number, the date of collection and the place of collection, and were then transported to the laboratory for weighing and storage. The whole fish were weighed and placed in plastic bags and stored in a freezer.

Wet digestion: Frozen fish samples were thawed and dissected. The pieces of edible muscle tissue, about (~10 g), were weighed accurately and placed in clean dry Erlenmeyer flasks which were closed with polyethylene stoppers. Sample flasks were digested in a constant temperature shaking water-bath at 58° until clear solution in nitric acid (reagent grade) was obtained (50-60 min). Sample flasks were removed from the bath and allowed to cool. The digests were diluted to 100 ml total volume with deionised water⁴.

Trace elements determination: The trace element contents of the digest were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer using a Perkin-Elmer 5000 and Perkin-Elmer 306 spectrophotometers². Determination of trace elements were measured as parts per million. Standard solution of each element was used in determination.

TABLE 1—TRACE ELEMENT LEVELS (ppm) IN SALTWATER FISH FROM THE ATLANTIC COAST OF SOUTH CAROLINA

Species	Whole body wt. g	Fe	Zn	Cu	Ni	Cr	Hg	Mn	Mg	Ca	Na	K
Sea bass	215.7	0.36	0.18	0.09	0.33	0.25	0.50	0.03	12.21	14.93	72.0	550
Sea bass	209.5	0.34	0.16	0.08	0.30	0.15	0.40	0.02	10.21	9.86	68.0	500
Whiting	167.2	0.34	0.32	0.08	0.10	0.15	0.50	0.03	11.99	23.90	79.5	500
Sheepshead	1 560.8	0.49	0.26	0.09	0.10	0.38	0.12	0.02	14.31	15.48	48.5	650
Mullet	446.3	0.72	0.16	0.05	0.20	0.40	0.15	0.12	14.42	30.10	75.5	600
Grouper	1 564.1	0.78	0.55	0.09	0.22	0.30	0.52	0.07	14.43	22.31	102.0	600
Grouper	744.5	0.63	0.25	0.04	0.20	0.10	0.12	0.04	10.18	12.68	59.5	500
Flounder	287.0	0.42	0.13	0.08	0.20	0.20	0.17	0.02	14.37	9.49	47.0	700
Dolphin fillet	363.6	0.74	0.24	0.13	0.15	0.20	0.20	0.11	9.48	10.82	30.0	200
Toad fish	611.2	0.57	0.19	0.10	0.25	0.15	0.21	0.05	10.40	6.99	24.5	700
Cod fillet	620.4	0.33	0.45	0.11	0.25	0.20	0.22	0.06	10.33	6.90	47.0	300
Red snapper	1 344.7	0.45	0.16	0.08	0.18	0.22	0.23	0.07	13.72	13.87	45.0	750
Red snapper	696.7	0.39	0.08	0.05	0.15	0.20	0.14	0.02	13.71	5.61	39.0	300
Silver snapper	230.0	0.48	0.19	0.10	0.15	0.45	0.32	0.02	15.03	8.90	57.0	700
Speckled trout	325.3	0.31	0.20	0.07	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.03	13.27	8.96	53.0	600